

A study on socio - economic condition of Paduke Kuteera workers under LIDKAR special reference to Bangalore

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 26 June 2026	The study focuses on socio- economic challenges faced by paduke Kuteera and LIDKAR showrooms workers problems regarding organizational challenges and employee welfare conditions and market demand downfall based on primary data collection collected from showroom employees and Paduke Kuteera workers in Rajajinagar Jayanagar, Nayandahalli, KHB colony, Basaveshwara Nagar in Bangalore the study concentrates on employees, social security support, sales enhancement strategy, marketing improvement, product innovation, government support for the growth of employees and work satisfaction, importance of skill development training programmes for upgradation in modern scenario and need of digital adaptation so that sustainability of workers in Paduke Kuteera associated with LIDKAR.
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INTRODUCTION

The Public Sector Undertakings play a predominant role in development of nation by creating more employment generating for the poor and marginal section employees. In that way LIDKAR is the one of the most important PSUs to upliftment of schedule caste community people by giving opportunity to start a business through Paduke kuteera for the well-trained footwear artisan in Bangalore and all over Karnataka by providing financial support in establishing Paduke Kuteera and LIDKAR showrooms. Large number of SC community leather articians were working collaborated with Paduke Kuteera under LIDKAR . This helps the weaker section to earn income and to become economically uplift themselves. but Post Covid have been affected heavily due to the lock down. No shops open and no proper social security support also because of the digital transition of lock down impact lot on paduke Kuteera people suddenly decline of demand for leather footwear in showroom. Due to lock down number of shops closed lack of digital marketing and people demand was more on trending style and varieties of leather products in footwear. Many customers shifted their taste and preferences towards attractive brands of footwear for the Padake workers decline of people direct purchase. The present study to examine the challenges faced by LIDKAR showrooms employees and Paduke Kuteera workers social economic condition, problems faced during post-Covid.

Research gap

The present research study focused to analyze the socio-economic condition and challenges faced by LIDKAR showroom, employees and Paduke kuteera workers in Bangalore.

Objectives

- To study the socio-economic condition of LIDKAR employees and padukr Kuteera workers.
- To analyze the Post Covid sales and market challenges faced by LIDKAR.
- To examine the impact of change in customers preference, leather product sale.
- To suggest measures for improving organizational sustainability and workers welfare.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The nature of the study adopted here is both descriptive and analytical for the study. Both primary and secondary data used primary data through prepared questionnaire and secondary data annual reports, journal books, company reports, Random sampling technique have been used. sampling size 50 respondents from LIDKAR showrooms and Paduke Kuteera in Rajajinagar, Jayanagar, KHB colony, Basaveshwara Nagar, Nayandahalli in Bangalore, statistical statistical tool are percentage method bar chart pie chart are used.

Data analysis and interpretation

Source : Survey April- May 2026

The majority of respondents were dissatisfied with employee welfare measures such as medical facility, provident fund, transportation, pension scheme organizational support such

as skill developing training programmes, no proper communication between higher management.

Source : Survey April- May 2026

The majority of employees stated that sales performance declined significantly after COVID-19 due to reduced customer demand and no proper marketing like online

expansion and old design foot wears no new brandings innovations.

Source : Survey April- May 2026

Most employees stated that customers increasingly prefer modern and youth-oriented leather products because of the style transition, many customers demand for kinds wear but the company unable to produce lack of customers taste and preferences goods are not available, so there is need of new collections of food wears for youths and kinds favorable.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- Majority of the employees were dissatisfied with existing social security measures schemes.
- No proper health security medical support because during lock down shops were closed. Due to that worker from Paduke Kuteera faced lot of problem.
- There is huge transition of digital marketing which let them Paduke kuteera d decreased demand for handmade footwear because of online services.
- LIDKAR showrooms sales declined to the emergence of other brands attraction of products.
- The LIDKAR showrooms faced huge fall in demand due to traditional design and old method of marketing, due to the change of taste and preferences, customer is dissatisfied with all the collection because of their private footwear brands, more attractive than LIDKAR prepared.

SUGGESTIONS

- Improve the employee social security measures by providing medical facility, PF facility, higher education support for the workers, children's
- Introduction or introduce of more digital upgradation in marketing and skill development and training programmes .
- For the workers innovative modern designs in footwear collection, especially for youths and kid with kids' footwear

- The government should fund the LIDKAR for the upgradation in technology and product differentiation and employee's welfare programmes

Recommendation changing scenario requires innovative strategy in protecting the public sector undertakings by upgrading the social security support, skill development program, change in product design and digital marketing growth for the sustainability of LIDKAR and Paduke Kuteera

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Karnataka leather industry development Corp Ltd and Paduke Kuteera employees faced major challenges like social security support from organizational market related problems, product design no proper skill development program for upgradation sudden fall of sale decline in income affected drastically, particularly among economically weaker section, dependent on leather related occupation. This study emphasis the importance of social security support, innovative strategy in changes of design in footwear require very important upgradation, digital marketing, employee welfare, innovative products, can improve their upliftment of workers associated with play LIDKAR.

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